

THE DESIGN OF MODERN WOMEN'S BAG WITH DOYO FIBER AND TUMPAR SULAM AS NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION METHOD

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The development of trends and fashion culture in woman's products is very massive. This development impacts the diversification of products in the market. Many foreign cultures influence Indonesian products, especially woman's products in the market, and these products are widely used among teenage women. Therefore, the existence of traditional culture seemed to be forgotten. This research aims to design a modern product while preserving traditional culture. The introduction of culture and cultural preservation is known as cultural knowledge. With qualitative methods and design by Vinod Goel, namely preliminary design, design development, and final design and prototype, a woman's bag was produced with the main material Ulap Doyo cloth embroidered Sulam Tumpar on it as the *Egretta Garzetta Linnaeus*, the fauna icon of East Kalimantan.

KEYWORDS:Woman's bag, cultural knowledge, Ulap Doyo, Sulam Tumpar, *Egretta Garzetta Linnaeus***INTRODUCTION**

The culture of society is growing up with the times. Society tends to lead to a consumptive culture, especially in fashion. According to Simmel (1899), Bourdieu (1996), Campbell (1987), Miller (1987), and Baudrillard (2000), the meaning of consumption is the psychological drive of humans to fulfill their needs, desire for the social environment and as a builder of cultural identity [1]. Prestige, trends, or just a collection motion are factors that encourage someone to buy goods [2]. Urban communities not only interpret goods as use-value but have shifted into a social meaning, reaching happiness, comfort, wealth, prestige, and modernity.

Fashion culture dramatically affects the psychology of women. One of them is the use of bags as a complement to women's fashion. Women will feel more confident if they are fully fashioned. Fashion is often associated with clothing, but actually, everything that is a trend in society can be defined as fashion. As an example, clothing, appetite, entertainment, consumer goods, and others. The function of fashion is not only to express non-verbal communication but is also used as a personal identity of the individual [3][4][5][6].

Communication is divided into verbal and non-verbal communication. Verbal communication is all symbols expressed directly in the form of words. Besides that, non-verbal communication is communication that is not directly stated in words. Non-verbal communication can be visual, proxemic or usage personal and social spaces, artifactual, and auditive non verbal messages [5]. Clothing is a way to communicate identity where this identity is also followed by compliance with regulations or the "moral" rules. Several complementary attributes (accessories, bags, shoes, etc.) are said to be a consequence of compliance with these regulations.

The flow rate of globalization has an impact on changing people's lifestyles more modern. Moreover, the influence of foreign cultures that easily enter through technology and communication has an impact on the shifting of cultural preservation values. Cultural values are slowly being eroded by the incoming foreign culture. It demands awareness and the role of the younger generation to continue to maintain the existence of local culture and inherit culture continuously amidst the flow of globalization[7]. According to Hildigardis [8], there are two ways to maintain and preserve culture, namely; Culture Experience and Culture Knowledge.

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OBJECTIVES

The focus of this research is on how to design a women's bag as a complement to fashion while still preserving the Dayak Benuaq culture of East Kalimantan by cultural experience and cultural knowledge. It is hoped that this research will add to the diversification of fashion products that prioritize the value of cultural preservation. This bag can be a companion for women to follow the current instant lifestyle [9].

METHODOLOGY

Weaving Doyo is a form of expression of the beliefs of the Benuaq Dayak people in East Kalimantan. Ulap Doyo Weaving is a type of tie weaving made of doyo leaf fiber (*Curliglia latifolia*). The raw material is leaves from pandanus-like plants that have strong fibers and grow wild in the interior of Kalimantan, one of which is in the Tanjung Isuy area, Jempang, West Kutai. Before being used as raw material for weaving, these leaves must be dried and sliced in the direction of the leaf fibers to form fine fibers. These fibers are then woven and twisted to form coarse threads.

Ulap Doyo weaving is made in a unique weaving process and goes through several challenging stages. The manufacturing process is passed down from generation to generation and must be preserved. Therefore, ulap doyo weaving has become a cultural symbol of East Kalimantan. Doyo ulap woven fabrics have many types of decorations that have meanings in each motif, for example, motifs of the dragon, which symbolizes the beauty of a woman. The development of the Ulap Doyo cloth design is to apply it with the embroidery tumpar. The various designs are developed to the beauty of the products produced[11]

This study uses a qualitative method in finding reference sources and the Vinod Goel method in designing bag designs. Vinod Goel (1995) formulated three stages of design, namely preliminary design, development design, final design & prototype. The Vinod Goel research method is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 : Design Method by Vinod Goel [12]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary Design

Cultural Experience and cultural knowledge are two ways of preserving culture. Cultural experience is a way of making something that has cultural value by directly involving the experience. While, cultural knowledge is carried out by using knowledge related to the culture that is used in certain forms such as fashion [8].

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Design Development

Market Analysis

A survey was carried out to 40 users based on demographic, geographic, and psychographic segmentation approaches in order to determine the target consumer market. The result is that bags are used by women at the age of 25-35 years who psychologically like to follow trends and fashion. Even though the design concept of this bag is traditional modern, which elevates the Dayak Banuaq culture of East Kalimantan, geographically this bag can be marketed nationally or internationally. This is intended to introduce the culture of East Kalimantan.

Activity Analysis

The activity and needs analysis is carried out as a reference for determining the configuration and specification of the bag design. The survey results obtained three results, they are:

- The bag has 1 main space and 1 companion space.
- the shape of bag is a sling bag
- The material of the bag is a Ulap Doyo material which is given a spool embroidery accessory

System Analysis

The lock system uses a zipper and magnetic button for the opening and closing system. A square ring system for connecting to the strap and bag ring E makes it easy for users to adjust the length of the bag strap. Stitch system using Key. Stitch is used because it is able to sew different fabrics thick.

Material Analysis

The modern traditional concept makes the bag has classic materials, such as leather and ulapdoyo fabrics. The combination of materials aims as a form of cultural knowledge.

Culture Analysis

The process of introducing the Dayak Benuaq culture in this bag design is the use of Ulap Doyo cloth combined with tumpar embroidery in the form of the icon of East Kalimantan's fauna[9].

Color Analysis

The color used is the natural color or the basic color of the ulapdoyo material. This is due to the adjustment to the concept of a bag which has a mission as cultural knowledge. However, the typical East Kalimantan logo design adapts the previous research [9].

Logo Analysis

The icon in this bag is the tumpar embroidery in the form of two typical East Kalimantan fauna named *Egretta garzetta Linnaeus* [13][14], which is designed with gestalt theory so that it is shaped like the shape of love [8]. This logo as a non-verbal communication that communicates about fauna in East Kalimantan.

Figure 2 : Species *Egretta Garzetta*

Linnaeus[13][14]

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Figure 3 : Gestalt Theory in *Egretta Garzetta Linnaeus* [9]

Design Sketch

Figure 4 : Design Sketch Alternative

Based on the average number of women who like sketches design of 4 design alternatives, the selected design is the first design, since the design is simple and energetic when it is used by young women at the age 25-35 years. This age is considered as the productive age for women.

Final design and prototype

Figure 5 : Final Design

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A survey of user tastes is carried out by distributing questionnaires online against existing design alternatives. 37% chose alternative 1, 22% chose alternative 2, 24% chose alternative 3, 17% chose alternative 4. The final design of the bag has the following specifications:

- The main raw material for doyo silk-woven cloth with embroidery accessories and a bird Egretta Garzetta Linnaeus.
- The addition of red accents to the bag list and bag straps made of Polyester gives an energetic impression and balances the basic color of doyo weaving.
- The bag configuration consists of 1 main slot and 1 small pocket on one side of the bag to give a simple impression.
- The bag is equipped with 1 retsliting as a bag opening and closing system.

The length of the bag strap is flexible because it can be adjusted with the E ring

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CONCLUSION

There were 4 alternative bag designs from the development of a bird motif design as the icon of East Kalimantan (Egretta Garzetta Linnaeus) which was modified on the front of the bag and the embroidery on the fabric. Based the average calculation, 37% of the women liked the first alternative design. Design fits the energetic concept, simple, but highlight the cultural values of the Dayak Benuaq of East Kalimantan as well as modern.

The Efforts to introduce regional culture is needed by developing diversification products with the concept of Cultural Knowledge by digging deeper into cultural information, both flora, fauna, and other characteristic of East Kalimantan.

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